

FACE RECOGNITION USING MACHINE LEARNING: A CRITICAL REVIEW

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ABSTRACT

Face detection, registration, and recognition have become a fascinating field for researchers. The motivation behind the enormous interest in the topic is the need to improve the accuracy of many real-time applications. Countless methodologies have been acknowledged and presented in the past years. The complexity of the human face visual and the significant changes based on different effects make it more challenging to design as well as implementing a powerful computational system for object recognition in addition to human face recognition. Using supervised learning often requires extensive training for the computer which results in high execution times. It is an essential step in the face recognition to apply strong preprocessing approaches such as face registration to achieve a high recognition accuracy rate. Although there are exist approaches do both detection and recognition, we believe the absence of a complete end-to-end system capable of performing recognition from an arbitrary scene is in large part due to the difficulty in alignment. Often, the face registration is ignored, with the assumption that the detector will perform a rough alignment, leading to suboptimal recognition performance. In this research, we presented an enhanced approach to improve human face recognition using a deep learning and features extraction based on the correlation between the training images.

Keywords: Features, dataset, deep learning.

I. INTRODUCTION

A biometric recognition system is an automated system that verifies or identifies a person using his physiological and / or behavioural characteristics [5]. The input of a face recognition system is an image or video stream and the output is an identification or verification of the subject or subjects that appear in the image or video database [6] defined a face recognition system as a three-stage process as shown in figure 1. In a face recognition system, face detection is the first stage prior to recognition. Face detection is the procedure to determine all the possible faces at different locations with different sizes in a given image. Face detection technique has numerous computer vision applications and is a model that includes several iterations. Face detection and localization are performed at the same time in some systems and in others face detection is first completed and then, if positive, face localization is accomplished. Thus, face detection is a two-class problem wherein a decision has to be made as to whether there is a face or not in the picture.

Fig-1: A basic Face Recognition System

Once the face is detected, the next stage is feature extraction that involves obtaining relevant facial features from the data. This stage finds application in facial feature tracking or emotion recognition. The features could be certain face regions, variations, angles as well as measures. By feature extraction, the number of resources required to define a large set of data are simplified. When the analysis is done with complex data, a greater number of variables lead to problems. It might also require a classification algorithm where the generalization could be poor to new samples. Figure 1.2 shows the process of feature extraction in an image.

Finally, the system enters the third stage to perform recognition where the task is to perform identification or verification. In an identification (one-to-many matching) task, the system would report an identity from a database. When an image of an unknown individual is given, the identity of the person can be determined by comparing it with the database of images of known individuals. In the verification (one-to-one matching) task,

when the image of an unknown individual along with a claim of identity, the task is to determine whether the individual is matched with the images in the database.

Fig-2: Face Detection and Facial Feature Extraction in a group photo

II. SCHEMES FOR FACE DETECTION

Matthew Turk et al. [15] used Principal Component Analysis (PCA), known as the Eigenfaces approach, to preprocess the Gray levels. A simple way to check whether an image is really of a face has been described. The technique involves transforming an image into face space and then transforming it back (reconstructing) into the original image space. It has been found that about forty eigenfaces are sufficient for a good description of human faces and the reconstructed image has few pixel-by-pixel errors. Alan L. Yuille et al. [36] demonstrated the face detection using templates whose sizes are variable (deformable templates). Instead of using several fixed size templates, a deformable template (which is non-rigid) was utilized and by changing the size of the template a face in an image could be detected. Extraction of human head and face boundaries and facial features automatically is critical in the areas of face recognition, criminal identification, security and surveillance systems, and Human Computer Interfacing (HCI). The concept of head and face boundary extraction for face detection applications was proposed by Ashok Samal et al. [14]

The efficient detection systems should be capable of eliminating the unwanted details like background and the areas other than face like hair that are not necessary to perform face recognition. It should be capable of extracting the useful information to perform the task. This is possible in still images by running a window across the image and is called the Window Based Technique for face detection. Roberto Brunelli et al. [13] described the usage of this technique to check the presence or absence of a face inside the window.

G. Burel et al. [12] proposed a Neural Network method for automatic detection and localization of faces on digital images. In the technique, a large number of training examples of faces and non-faces are compressed into fewer examples. The method of Multiresolution Analysis and Learning by Example has been used in the method. The management of the learning data has to be taken care of to improve the performance.

Penio S Penev et al. [8] proposed Local Feature Analysis (LFA) to encode the local topological structure of face images. LFA is considered as a local method as it utilizes a set of kernels to implicitly detect the local structure such as eyes, nose and mouth. According to Guangzheng Yang et al. [11], the face detection methods can be categorized into four types namely, knowledge-based, feature invariant based, appearance-based, and template matching based. The facial features have been modelled in a simple way as two symmetric eyes, a nose in the middle and a mouth underneath in the knowledge-based method as observed by Yang and Huang (1997).

III. LITERATURE REVIEW

Edward H. Adelson et al. [17] note that in human vision, dynamic energy seems to be coded in a set of transformed axes. Athanasios Nikolaidis et al. [9] developed an approach by combining Adaptive Hough Transform, Template Matching, Active Contour Model, and Projective Geometry properties. Adaptive Hough

Transform was used for curve detection, Template Matching for locating the facial features, Active Contour Model for detecting the face contour, and Projective Geometry properties for exact posture determination.

A. Lanitis et al. [7] has describe the use of flexible models for representing the shape and grey-level appearance of human faces. These models are controlled by a small number of parameters which can be used to code the overall appearance of a face for image compression and classification purposes.

In 2000, Turk and Pentland et al. [6], have proposed the popular Eigen-faces method for face recognition. Deep learning uses the Eigen-Faces to represents human face images as a subset of their Eigen Vectors. Guangzheng Yang et al. [11] has proposed Kernel FLD for human face recognition, which they called Kernel Fisher-face and Kernel Eigen-face methods. The Alexnet in deep learning is better than conventional PCA in terms of recognition accuracy and is computationally more efficient than PCA therefore; it can improve the process time of image feature extraction significantly.

Timo Ahonen et al. [4] suggested a new method for face representation using texture analysis. The Local Binary Pattern (LBP) that originated from texture analysis has been used for the representation. Jin Ok Kim et al. [3] present a method for a template matching and an efficient cascaded object detection. The proposed method belongs to wide criteria which can regard to the “feature-centric”. Furthermore, the proposed cascade method has some merits to the face changes. Zhengyou Zhang et al. [2] stated that the Face detection has been one of the most studied topics in the computer vision literature.

Yongjing Lin et al. [1] stated that the Automatic facial gender recognition is a widely used task in the field of computer vision, which is very easy for a human, but very challenging for computers. In this paper, a face gender classification algorithm based on face recognition feature vectors is proposed. Firstly, face detection and pre-processing are performed on the input images, and the faces are adjusted to a unified format. Secondly, the face recognition model is used to extract feature. it achieves a recognition rate of 97.4% on the Asian star face dataset, outperforming existing methods, which shows that the proposed method is helpful for the research of facial gender.

IV. PROBLEM STATEMENT

Face recognition is one of the most successful applications of image analysis and understanding. Hence, it has gained major attention owing to its extensive commercial and law enforcement applications and also due to the availability of possible technologies after several years of investigations as explained by W. Zhao et al. [5]. A number of face recognition algorithms have been proposed for the past two decades as well as various face representation methods based on global features, including a great number of subspace-based methods and some spatial frequency techniques.

Face is one of the most common parts used by people to recognize each other. Over the course of its evolution, the human brain has developed highly specialized areas dedicated to the analysis of the facial images. The reliability of face recognition has increased significantly, but it is still not always accurate. The ability to correctly classify the image depends on a variety of variables including lighting, pose, facial expressions and image quality.

Henry A. Rowley et al. [10] first introduced a complete automatic version of a face detection system. It suffered from the drawback of very low recognition rate, even for small database images. However, the acceptable results may be obtained if these features are extracted manually. This prototype continued for nearly thirty years even though the recognition rates were low even on small data sets.

Some of the methods propose a face recognition system using geometrical features. The geometrical features such as nose width and length, mouth position and chin shape were computed from the face. These features are matched with the features of known individuals. Euclidean Distance was used to find the closest match. The advantage of this method is that recognition is possible even at very low resolutions and with noisy images.

However, the automated extraction of the facial geometrical features is difficult.

Some authors have investigated and determined that the performance of face recognition systems is affected by strong variations in pose and illumination. It was found that the variation between images of different faces is smaller than the images of the same face captured in a variety of environments. This implies that the changes induced by illumination could be larger than the differences between individuals, causing systems based on comparing images to misclassify the identity of the input image.

Most of the authors suggested techniques for comparing the face recognition methods using Neural Networks and Neuro-Fuzzy. Feature extraction is performed using curvelet transform. Feature vector is obtained by extracting statistical quantities of curve coefficients. The technique is time consuming since most of the time is spent in training the network.

V. CONCLUSION

The researchers moved toward a deep learning-based image registration approaches because of the classical image registration limitation. P. Gadde et al. proposed an Image registration with artificial neural networks using spatial and frequency features. In their study, the registration of images is investigated with two novel neural network-based approaches, namely, SIFT-DCT and SIFT-DWT. Scale-invariant Feature Transform (SIFT), Discrete Cosine Transform (DCT), and Discrete Wavelet Transform (DWT) are employed in these approaches.

Both new approaches combine features in the spatial domain (SIFT) and frequency domain (DCT or DWT) to provide more robust feature extraction methods for image registration. The learning ability and nonlinear mapping ability of artificial neural network provide a flexible and intelligent tool for data fusion on feature matching and transform model parameter estimation. However, this proposed method obtains the training data using original methods not based on deep learning.

Table-1: Comparison of detection rate for different methods

S. No.	Method of Face Detection	Algorithm used	Detection Rate (FP - False Positive)
1	Colmenarez and Huang et al. (1997)	Maximum Discrimination based	93.9% (at 8122 FP) with CMU dataset
2	Sung & Poggio et al. (1998)	Example based learning	81.9% (at 13 FP) with MIT dataset
3	Rowley et al. (1998)	Neural Network based	86.2% (at 23 FP) with CMU dataset
4	Schneiderman-Kanade et al. (2000)	Example based learning	94.4% (at 65 FP) with CMU datasets
5	Yang et al. (2002)	LDA based method	92.3% (at 82 FP) with CMU dataset
6	Li and Zhang et al. (2004)	Float Boost based learning	90.2% (at 31 FP) with MIT+CMU datasets
7	Viola and Jones et al. (2004)	Adaboost (Haar like features)	93.9% (at 167 FP) with MIT dataset
8	Mita et al. (2005)	Adaboost (joint Haar like features)	94% (at 48 FP) with MIT+CMU datasets
9	Safi Yadahalli et al. (2017)	Adaboost	98.13% with a STPT Training dataset

VI. REFERENCES

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